

Moving Towards Total Cabin Filtration: Filtering the Fresh Air Supply

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ABBREVIATIONS

CAT	Clean air technology
HEPA	High efficiency particulate air
VOCs	Volatile organic compounds
A-CAF	Advanced cabin air filters

ABSTRACT

On occasion, engine related contamination is able to enter the aircraft cabin as part of the fresh air supply, this can result in reduced air quality and expensive delays and schedule disruptions. Pall Aerospace are developing a filtration system, Clean Air Technology (CAT) that will remove this contamination from the fresh air supply before it is able to reach the cabin or cockpit.

Pall has been serving the aerospace industry for over 70 years with innovative, enabling products. Pall was the first company to develop and introduce hospital-grade (H14) High Efficiency Particulate Air (HEPA) filters in the aircraft cabin air recirculation line and Pall Aerospace now proudly leads the way in the development and introduction of advanced cabin air filters designed to remove additional contaminants present in the cabin such as odors and volatile organic compounds (VOCs).

Airlines are constantly looking at ways to improve their operation. Statistics show that about a third of delays are due to events not associated with weather or air traffic control (ATC). These delays include fume events, where

noxious odors are detected in the cockpit or passenger cabin.

The frequency of reported air quality incidents has increased over the years and this increase is due not to age-related deteriorating aircraft performance but more to an increased awareness of cabin air quality among flight crew and passengers and also improved crew training related to reporting procedures for fume events.¹ For example, one airline experienced a 5-fold increase in the number of reported incidents after completion of crew training; however, this number was subsided once mitigation procedures were introduced.

While VOCs are generated from many sources, including sources inside the cabin, the VOCs from engine fluids, primarily lube oils, create the most concerns in the industry. These VOCs can stem from oil leaking past seals into the hot engine bleed air. The vaporization, partial oxidation, or combustion of that oil creates VOCs, some of which are or can become toxic.^{2,3} Since engine bleed air is used for the fresh air supply, these VOCs can then enter the cabin and cockpit. Fume events are disruptive because identifying an errant smell is time consuming and crew members are not always able to detect the source.

Despite the relative rarity of fume events, they occur frequently enough that the cost of disruption (~ \$50,000) is of concern to many airlines.⁴ For example, FAST, the Airbus technical magazine, pointed out in 2013 that “a noticeable cabin odor can be generated from ingesting only a very small amount of oil.” Bad smells worry passengers, and crews may delay take-off until these dissipate. The longer the odor lingers, the longer the delay. In the worst cases, a flight will be cancelled or, if already airborne, diverted, which can cost an airline a significant amount of money. The British government estimated a fume event occurs roughly once in every 2,000 flights, which equates to 50 fume events per day worldwide. A 2002 report by the U.S. National Research Council quoted 1.29 air quality events per 1,000 flights for the Airbus A320 and in a report by Dr Shahadi it was estimated over five bleed air related events occur every

day in the US.⁵

A-CAFs

A number of airlines have taken steps and introduced new procedures to improve cabin air quality. These new steps include the installation of advanced cabin air filters (A-CAF). These filters minimize schedule disruption by shortening the dissipation period of an odor. Laboratory tests and test on an aircraft of a US airline have shown that odors dissipate three times faster in a cabin protected by A-CAF compared to cabins that do not have A-CAF installed.

Pall’s A-CAF products are specifically designed for aerospace applications. Pall partnered with a specialty chemical manufacturer to develop a synthetic carbon adsorbent material that targets the contaminants of concern in aircraft bleed air while maintaining performance over a long life to meet the existing changeout interval of the original HEPA filters and airline maintenance schedules. The synthetic carbon also has a low sensitivity to humidity and is presented in the filter such that it has an extremely low pressure drop, both of which enhance to its high life.

Figure 1 shows the high-level process of how the adsorbent material is manufactured. A select blend of polymers is chosen based on the adsorption performance requirements of the target VOCs. These

polymers are formed into spherical beads using a proprietary process, and the beads are then pyrolyzed and activated using high temperature steam. These beads are then formed into a low pressure drop and stable matrix.

These synthetic carbon adsorbent materials outperform many conventional materials such as natural-substrate activated carbon due to higher surface area per unit mass as well as the tailored surface chemistry created by the choice of starting material and the activation process. Pore size and pore size distribution is important as these are direct measures of the amount of surface area available for VOC adsorption (larger pores mean less surface area which means less VOC capacity) while surface chemistry controls the “stickiness” of the pore wall for different ranges of VOCs.

Most VOC molecules are extremely small; for example, Toluene is ~0.2 nm therefore a high volume of micro and mesopores provide the optimum adsorbent performance. The accepted method of assessing pore size and volume is using BET analysis. Pall’s bespoke synthetic carbon adsorbent has more micropore and macropore surface area as compared to standard, coconut shell activated carbon and over 22% more internal surface area (~1339 m²/g vs ~1,092 m²/g). Table 1 shows the calculate BET values.

Figure 3 shows SEM images of standard coconut

Sample ID	Surface area (m ² /g)	Micro pore area (m ² /g)	Meso pore area (m ² /g)	Total pore volume (cc/g)	Micro pore volume (cc/g)	Avg. pore dia. (Å)	Data correlation to model
Synthetic carbon	1339 ± 67	1174	165	0.645	0.441	19.3	99.90%
Coconut shell	1092 ± 57	945	147	0.53	0.359	19.4	99.90%
% Synthetic to coconut shell	23%	24%	12%	22%	23%	N/A	N/A

Table 1 – BET Values

Figure 3 – SEM Images of Standard Coconut Carbon

Figure 4 – Pall's Bespoke Synthetic Carbon Adsorbent

carbon and Figure 4 shows Pall's bespoke synthetic carbon adsorbent. Figure 5 shows a transmission electron microscope (TEM) image of the two materials. The difference in pore size distribution and the "wasted space" of the natural carbon is immediately evident in the images.

Pall tested full sized filters made from both natural activated carbon and our bespoke adsorbent using test parameters equivalent to those found in commercial, single aisle aircraft. Figure 6 shows the relative performance of the two filters over a period of an hour. This test shows the divergence in efficiency between the two materials. The bespoke adsorbent is still over 90% efficient after exposure while the natural carbon is less

than 60% efficient.

Advanced cabin air filters are more expensive than traditional HEPA cabin air filters, therefore it is important that they demonstrably achieve their performance goals.

The A-CAF filters must fit in the same form factor as the original recirculation filters, which necessitates a small reduction in the capacity of the HEPA filter. As an important requirement for the airlines is to maintain a similar changeout interval, significant on-wing testing has to be performed to ensure that the addition of the VOC adsorbent material did not impact product life. The only true means of establishing the changeout interval

Synthetic carbon has significantly less void (wasted) space.

Figure 5 — A TEM image of the two materials

Figure 6 — Relative performance of the two filters

is to determine the performance of a number of filters over thousands of hours in service. Figure 7 shows the results of these types of tests for an A330 A-CAF. All of the data points shown represent tests on filters used on commercial aircraft. The blue line shows the data that was generated from the original trials in the late 1990's which were used by Airbus to set the changeout interval. Results from trials on the latest standard of filters are

shown in the red band and it can easily be seen that the life of the HEPA layer of today's A-CAF filters, due to improved manufacturing processes as well as the elimination of smoking, will easily meet the HEPA-only MPD interval of 5,000 hours.

The other factor in determining the life of the filter is the carbon efficiency. Figure 8 shows tests on filters used

Figure 7 – Results of these type of tests for an A330 A-CAF

Figure 8 – Tests on filters used on commercial aircraft

European Short Haul: 660 Flight Hours - Reported Fume Event

Total 69049 µg/g

Methoc Compound	Quantity µg/g	% of Total	Comments
1 CS2 Est Cyclopentasiloxane, decamethyl-	33209	48.10	Cosmetics, hair spray, skin care products
2 CS2 Est Limonene	4145.8	6.00	Cosmetics, fragrances, cleaning agents
3 CS2 Est Cyclohexanol, 5-methyl-2-(1-methylethyl)-, (1.alpha.,2.beta.,5.alpha.)-(+/-)-	2569.5	3.72	Topical medicines, perfumes
4 CS2 Est Cyclohexasiloxane, dodecamethyl-	1761.1	2.55	Personal care products, solvent
5 CS2 Est Dodecane	1751.9	2.54	Jet fuel related
6 CS2 Est Isopropyl myristate	1719.9	2.49	Solvent for perfumes, skin care products
7 CS2 Est Undecane	1465.6	2.12	Aircraft fluid related
8 CS2 Est Tridecane	1355	1.96	Jet fuel related
9 CS2 Est Cyclotetrasiloxane, octamethyl-	1122.7	1.63	Cosmetics, personal care products, cleaning agents
10 CS2 Est Homosalate	1115.5	1.62	Common component of sunscreen
11 CS2 Est Decane	1029.7	1.49	Jet fuel related
12 CS2 Ex Tributyl phosphate	990.9	1.44	Component of aircraft hydraulic fluid
13 CS2 Est 2,2,4-Trimethyl-1,3-pentanedil diisobutrate	837.6	1.21	Plasticiser, adhesives and sealants
14 CS2 Est Pentadecane	827.1	1.20	Jet fuel related
15 CS2 Est 2-Ethylhexyl salicylate	775.4	1.12	Cosmetics and sunscreens
16 CS2 Est o-Xylene	734.4	1.06	
17 280 TD Toluene	676.5	0.98	
99 280 TD 6-Methylthieno[2,3-b]pyridine	1.8	0.00	
100 280 TD Benzophenone	1.3	0.00	
280 TD Phosphoric acid, tris(2-methylphenyl) ester	1.3	0.00	Tri-Cresyl Phosphate
102 280 TD 7-Hexadecene, [Z]-	1.2	0.00	
103 120 TD Isopropyl Alcohol	1.2	0.00	
104 120 TD 4-Methyldocosane	1	0.00	
105 120 TD Ethanone, 1,1-(2,6-dimethyl-3,5-pyridinediyl)bis-	1	0.00	
106 280 TD Phthalic acid, isopropyl propyl ester	1	0.00	
107 280 TD 1-Pentadecene	0.7	0.00	
108 280 TD 9,10-Anthracenedione, 1,4-dimethyl	0.7	0.00	
109 120 TD 1-(2-Hydroxyethoxy)-2-(vinylthio)ethane	0.6	0.00	
110 120 TD 1-(2-Hydroxyethylthio)-2-(2-vinylthioethoxy)ethane	0.5	0.00	
111 280 TD o-Terphenyl	0.5	0.00	
112 280 TD 2H-Benzimidazol-2-one, 1,3-dihydro-5-methyl-(Dimethyl)[4-(2-phenyl-1,9b-dihydro-5-oxa-3,3a-diazacyclopenta[a]naphthalen-4-yl)phenyl]-amine	0.1	0.00	
113 280 TD 1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, mono(1-methylethyl) ester	0.1	0.00	

Table 2 – Analysis of the Filters

on commercial aircraft. The blue line is again the original trial data and this shows that the carbon efficiency when challenged with toluene is reduced to zero at around 2500 hours and this was the data used by Airbus in setting the original changeout interval. The red band shows most recent performance of the A330 A-CAF when challenged with Toluene against service hours and the green band shows the performance of the same filters when challenged with Limonene. In both cases the performance of the filters is much better than the original trial and this is due to optimization of the adsorbent and also to the elimination of smoking which reduces the adsorbent life.

Limonene was chosen as a test agent as it has a boiling point of 176°C which is more representative of the engine-based VOC's that are found in the cabin than toluene which boils at 110°C.

The VOC that have been deemed the most harmful boil even higher at over 250°C and although not shown on the chart the efficiency of the carbon against these VOC's is an order higher again, these higher boiling point VOC also do not desorb at the temperatures they filter operates at in the cabin.

The VOC removal efficiency of any adsorbent degrades over life. The estimated time to clear a fume event increases from ~2.5 minutes with a fresh filter to (~ one cabin air exchange interval) to ~5.5 minutes after 6,000 flight hours (~2 cabin air changes).

Part of the service Pall provide to the airlines is an analysis of the filters to determine what contaminants have been removed and retained on the filter from the cabin and cockpit. A sample of this data is shown in Table 2. Key to note are a) TBP, a product of hydraulic fluid, is always present on every filter tested and b) TCP has been identified on filters from aircraft that have experienced a fume event.

PUREcabin

It is important to note that installation of A-CAF will not stop the source of the problem and prevent odors and VOC's in the bleed air entering the cabin.

However, there are developments underway that will prevent engine related odors from reaching the cabin and cockpit and Pall is pleased to provide this short status update on our efforts.

A-CAF improves filtration of the recirculated air. While this creates a significant improvement in the cabin air quality, it does not address the source of the contaminated air in the cabin.

Fume events, engine related odors, and engine generated VOCs can be stopped from entering the cabin and cockpit if the fresh air supply is filtered. Pall is developing a total cabin filtration system (fresh and recirculated). Such a system will dramatically improve cabin air quality and eliminate the problems and issues associated with VOCs in the cabin air. Pall expects to have our first such product available for the A320 by the end of 2018.

Pall is also developing a sensor technology that can identify the presence of VOCs in the bleed and cabin air and identify their source. The sensor will be able to categorize and odor and identify its source. We also anticipate that it may be possible to predict the onset of a mechanical issue and enable preventative maintenance to take place.

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